

WPS OFFICE FOR BEGINNERS

What is WPS?

WPS is a Word Processing Software that allows you to create various documents such as letters, fliers, and reports...

Understanding The Word Interface

- Using the Quick Access Toolbar, you can access usual commands regardless of the tab you are currently on. In addition to Save, Undo, Redo, Open, Export, Print, and Print Preview, it includes the Save, Undo, Redo, and Open commands by default. Depending on your preferences, you can add other options.
 - Each command in this group belongs to a different command group. Any option can be applied by clicking on it. Some groups also have an arrow in the bottom-right corner, which you can click to see even more commands.
- Ruler: The Ruler is at the top of your document. It makes it easier to make alignment, spacing, and adjustments.
- You will find all the commands you need to perform the usual tasks in WPS on the Ribbon. It has multiple tabs, each with several groups of options.

- **The Ribbon:** uses a *tabbed ribbon system* instead of traditional menus. The **Ribbon** contains *multiple tabs*, each with several *groups of commands*. You will use these tabs to perform the most *usual tasks* in WSP.
- **Home tab:** allows you access to some of the most frequently used commands for working with WPS, including *copying, pasting, formatting, aligning paragraphs, and choosing document styles*.
- The **Home tab** is selected by default whenever you open Word.
- **Insert tab:** allows you to insert *pictures, charts, tables, shapes, cover pages, and more* to your document, which can help you *communicate* information visually and add *style* to your document.
- **Design tab:** gives you access to a variety of design tools, including *document formatting, effects, and Page borders:* which can give your document a polished look.
- **Page Layout tab:** allows you to change the *print formatting* of your document, including *margin width, page orientation, page breaks, and more*. When preparing to print a document, these commands will be essential.
- The **References tab** allows you to add *footnotes and citations* to your document. *Tables of contents, captions, and bibliographies* can be added. When writing academic papers, these commands can be helpful. Mail Merge lets you write letters, address envelopes, and create labels using the **Mailings tab**.

This is particularly useful for sending letters to multiple recipients at the same time. The **Review tab** provides access to Word's powerful editing features, such as adding comments and tracking changes. Document sharing and collaboration are made easy with these features.

- The **View tab:** allows you to switch between different views of your document and split the screen to view two halves of a document simultaneously. These commands will also be helpful when preparing to print a document.

- **Contextual tabs:** will appear on the **Ribbon** when working with certain items, such as tables, texts, and pictures. These tabs contained special command groups that can help you format these items as needed.
- **The Quick Access toolbar:** Located just above the Ribbon, the Quick Access toolbar lets you access common commands no matter which tab is selected. By default, it shows the Save, Undo, and Repeat commands. You can add other commands depending on your preference.
- **To add commands to the Quick Access toolbar:** Click the drop-down arrow to the right of the Quick Access toolbar. Select the command you wish to add from the drop-down menu. To choose from more commands, select More Commands.
- The command will be added to the Quick Access toolbar
- **Backstage view:** gives you various options for saving, opening a file, printing, and sharing your document. To access Backstage view: Click the File tab on the Ribbon. Backstage view will appear.
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